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Long-Term Joint EU-AU Research
and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy

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RES Potential Analysis

Work Package 3

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Kommentiert [KB1]: Honestly cant get the spacing right, can you give it a try please.

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Disclaimer

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Summary

The overall objective of the Open Access AU-EU Ecosystem for Energy System Modelling (OASES) project is the development and demonstration of a sustainable AU-EU ecosystem for energy system modelling, based on open-source software and open access data. The project consists of five interlinked work packages (WPs), each divided into several subtasks.

This report is the second deliverable within Work Package 3 (WP3), namely a report on a methodology for downscaling climate data to the required spatial and temporal scales for use in localized energy system modelling, and the derivation of an accompanying time series of wind and solar PV generation profiles.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form (format for easy transfer of data between different computer systems / packages)
OASES	Open Access AU-EU Ecosystem for Energy System Modelling
POW	Power of wind (or just wind power)
PV	Photo Voltaic
TOA	Top of Atmosphere (with relation to solar irradiance)
WAD	Wind Atlas Data
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The overall objective of the **Open Access AU-EU Ecosystem for Energy System Modelling (OASES)** project is the development and demonstration of a sustainable AU-EU ecosystem for energy system modelling, based on open-source software and open access data. The project aimed to build easy-to-use modelling workflows for different spatial scales, utilizing RES data developed in the project as well as data and tools from other similar high-quality efforts. It was planned that these workflows will be used by six example case studies, each with different scope, using code, data, tutorials, and documentation from the project's different work packages. By so doing, the project intended to enable local actors to learn and perform energy system scenario analysis relevant for their needs.

The work plan of the project is based on five work packages (WPs), each divided into several subtasks. Figure 1 gives an overview of the structure and lead partners of the work packages.

Figure 1. Overview of the structure and lead partners of the work packages

This report is the second deliverable within Work Package 3 (WP3). WP 3 covers several tasks, starting with a resource assessment (available data, software and methods) and ending with the generation of high-resolution RES time series. This deliverable responds to D3.2, titled *Description of the general model for wind power and solar PV time series generation for any future scenario*.

This report provides a technical description of the WP3 tasks related to the downscaling and interpolation of climate data, as well the translation of hourly climate data into a time series for solar PV or wind turbine power generation. The intention of this report is that a user can work through the report when applying the methods for a particular, selected local area.

2. Overview of this document

In Work Package 3 of this project the aim was to prepare solar photo voltaic (PV) and wind power time series data for electricity modelling scenarios. This is done by:

- Downloading meteorological time series data

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- Downscaling the data to the target 1km x 1km spatial resolution and 1 hour temporal resolution.
- Calculating the variables required for the time series generation.
- Generating an input Network Common Data Form (NetCDF) file.
- Calculating the power generation time series.

The steps are illustrated in Figure 2, below. The various technical steps in this figure, to be followed in sequence, are described in detail in this report.

Figure 2. Overview of technical steps

This report describes all the steps in appropriate detail in the various sections of the report. Section 3 deals with downloading the data, section 4 with the spatial interpolation, section 5 with the calculation of Atlite variables, Section 6 with the creation of the NetCDF file, and section 7 ends the report with a description of the determination of the power time series. It is possible for a user to focus on only one section or on all sections. However, the intention of this report is to provide an overview of all steps. By working through this report, a user should gain an understanding of how the various methodologies work and be able to generate a power generation time series to use in user defined scenarios.

3. Downloading the Data

The first step is to download data for the desired area and time duration. The Copernicus Climate Data Store (cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home) can be used to obtain ERA5 reanalysis data for all the variables required to calculate wind and solar potential.

The data can be downloaded manually through the Copernicus website, or an API combined with a Python script can be used to automate the download (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api-how-to>).

```
## Define Location of interest
location = [
    -33, 18, -34, 19,
]

## Define Date
date = {'year': '2019',
        'month': ['11', '12'],
        'day': ['01', '02', '03', '04', '05', '06', '07', '08', '09', '10',
                '11', '12', '13', '14', '15', '16', '17', '18', '19', '20',
                '21', '22', '23', '24', '25', '26', '27', '28', '29', '30',
                '31']}

## Define Time
time = ['00:00', '01:00', '02:00',
        '03:00', '04:00', '05:00',
        '06:00', '07:00', '08:00',
        '09:00', '10:00', '11:00',
        '12:00', '13:00', '14:00',
        '15:00', '16:00', '17:00',
        '18:00', '19:00', '20:00',
        '21:00', '22:00', '23:00',
]
```

Figure 3. Defining the parameters of the data to be downloaded.

The product type and variables of interest are listed in the Python script together with the date, time, and area of interest.


```
import cdsapi
c = cdsapi.Client(quiet=False,debug=True)

c.retrieve('reanalysis-era5-single-levels',
          {
            'product_type': 'reanalysis',
            'variable': [
              '100m_u_component_of_wind',
              '100m_v_component_of_wind',
              '2m_temperature',
              'forecast_surface_roughness',
              'geopotential',
              'runoff',
              'soil_temperature_level_4',
              'surface_net_solar_radiation',
              'surface_solar_radiation_downwards',
              'toa_incident_solar_radiation',
              'total_sky_direct_solar_radiation_at_surface',
            ],
            'year': date['year'],
            'month': date['month'],
            'day': date['day'],
            'time': time,
            'area': location,
            'format': 'netcdf',
          },
```

Figure 4. Python code used to download the ERA5 data.

A data download speed test was conducted using a DELL LATITUDE 5511 laptop and a 20-28 Mbps internet connection for different time periods and area sizes to estimate the optimal parameters. The results are presented in Table 1.

Time period (hour)	Area size (number of pixels)	Total number of data points	Download time
24	25 (5x5)	600	3.99 seconds
48	25	1 200	4.99 seconds
72	25	1 800	4.17 seconds
168 (1 week)	25	4 200	4.48 seconds
720 (1 month)	25	18 000	8.59 minutes

Time period (hour)	Area size (number of pixels)	Total number of data points	Download time
1464 (2 months)	25	36 600	14.57 minutes
4416 (6 months)	25	110 400	49.08 minutes
168 (1 week)	49 (7x7)	8 232	2.03 minutes
168	81 (9x9)	13 608	2.02 minutes
168	289 (17x17)	48 552	5.2 seconds
168	441 (21x21)	74 088	2.02 minutes
168	625 (25x25)	105 000	2.02 minutes
168	1681 (41x41)	282 408	2.05 minutes

Table 1. Speed test for data download.

From these results it can be seen that larger date and/or time ranges have a significantly larger influence compared to area size. This is due to more time steps equating to more files to download versus less but larger files.

4. Spatial Interpolation

4.1 Methods

4.1.1 Bilinear interpolation

Bilinear interpolation is a method used to estimate values of a point within a grid or a 2D space based on the values of surrounding points. It's commonly used in computer graphics, image processing, and various mathematical applications where you need to approximate the value of a function between two known data points. Bilinear interpolation assumes that the relationship between the points is linear both horizontally and vertically.

If you want to estimate the value at a point between these four points, bilinear interpolation considers the weights of the nearby points based on their distances. The closer a point is to the target location, the more its value contributes to the interpolated value.

Mathematically, bilinear interpolation can be expressed as follows:

$$Q = (1 - s)(1 - t)A + s(1 - t)B + (1 - s)tC + stD$$

Q is the interpolated value at the target point.

A, B, C, and D are the values of the four surrounding points.

s is the horizontal distance from the left point A to the target point.

t is the vertical distance from upper point A to the target point.

Bilinear interpolation was used to aggregate and disaggregate the ERA 5 data. Reanalysis data ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$) was aggregated to $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ (X1). Ensemble data ($0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$) was disaggregated to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ (Y1). Reanalysis data (X1) was disaggregated to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ (X2). $\Delta = Y1/X2$. This was done to find relative deviations.

Figure 5. a) ERA 5 ensemble data, (b) downscaled ERA 5 ensemble data (27.75 × 27.75), (c) ERA 5 reanalysis data, (d) downscaled ERA 5 reanalysis data (1km × 1km).

4.1.2 Kriging

Kriging is a spatial interpolation method that makes use of limited sampled data to approximate a continuous spatial field. It models the spatial variance of raw data and then provides estimates of the values at specific points across the region, where the spatial variation is considered to be statistically consistent. It assumes that an attribute's spatial variation is codetermined by random error, offsets and spatial autocorrelation factors instead of being completely random or completely determined. Spatial dependence of variables is necessary when kriging. [1]

Kriging is considered the best unbiased linear interpolation [1]. This means that:

1. It achieves the smallest difference between the real and estimated value. In other words, minimizing the variance.

2. The expectation of the real and estimated value is the same. In other words, the expectation of the errors is zero, and it is unbiased.
3. The estimated value is formed from a linear combination of weighted values.

In this case, kriging is performed using the R-package, KrigR [2]. This is a statistical downscaling tool that makes use of three steps. The first step is to download ERA5 data. The second step is to obtain co-variate data. The third step is to perform kriging. This tool allows for multi-core processing to reduce computational time as an optional argument.

In the first step, data for the region of interest is downloaded. To accomplish this, the following is required:

- The extent of the region of interest. This can be in the form of longitude and latitude co-ordinates or from a shapefile.
- The variable of interest. More information about the variables is provided in Section 0.
- The dates of interest. The start and end date indicate the period in which data should be downloaded. More information about download time related to time periods is provided in Section 3.
- The temporal resolution and step of interest (e.g., "hour" and "1" for hourly data)
- The API User and Key, which can be freely obtained from the Climate Data Store (CDS) [3].

```
library(KrigR)

Extent_ext <- extent(c( 24, 26,-29.5,-27.5))
Dir.Data <- "D:/Location/of/Data" # folder path for data

QS_Raw <- download_ERA(
  Variable = "100m_v_component_of_wind",
  DataSet = "era5-single-levels",
  DateStart = "2019-11-01",
  DateStop = "2019-12-31",
  TResolution = "hour",
  TStep = 1,
  Extent = Extent_ext,
  Dir = Dir.Data,
  FileName = "100m_u_component_of_wind_RAW",
  API_User = API_User,
  API_Key = API_Key
)
```

Figure 6. Code to download ERA5 data in R.

The option to save the ERA5 raw downloaded data temporarily or permanently is available. The next step is to download co-variate data and perform pre-processing. In this step, variograms are fitted to the raw downloaded data. Variograms describe the spatial geometry and dependence of regionalised variables [4], which is the basis of objective statistical spatial weights for interpolation. This establishes covariance functions with the co-variate data at the resolution of the raw downloaded data from step one. The relationship between the spatial autocorrelation of the raw downloaded data and the co-variables are described by these functions [2].


```
Covs_ls <- download_DEM(
  Train_ras = QS_Raw,
  Target_res = .009,
  Dir = Dir.Covariates,
  Keep_Temporary = TRUE
)
```

Figure 7. Download co-variate data from GMTED2010 in R.

The co-variate data provided by KrigR is the Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) [5]. This is a digital elevation model (DEM) on a 30 arcsecond resolution, which is approximately 900 m. The reason for this choice is due to the close relationship between elevation and other climate variables [6]. KrigR downloads the co-variate data and masks it to the user's defined region of interest. It then aggregates the data to the resolution of the raw downloaded data and the target resolution. As before, the data can be permanently saved to avoid unnecessary repeated downloads.

In the third step, kriging is performed. This is done through the R-package automap [7]. The downscaled output is saved as a NetCDF file at the target resolution specified in the previous step. The kriging estimates, as well as the standard errors of estimates, are provided in map format. This is possible due to kriging retaining the variances when fitting the variogram to the raw data [2].

```
QS_Krig <- krigR(
  Data = QS_Raw, # data we want to krig as a raster object
  Covariates_coarse = Covs_ls[[1]], # training covariate as a raster object
  Covariates_fine = Covs_ls[[2]], # target covariate as a raster object
  Keep_Temporary = FALSE, # we don't want to retain the individually kriged layers
  nmax = 40, # degree of localisation
  Cores = 10, # we want to krig using 10 cores to speed this process up
  FileName = "100m_u_component_of_wind_KRIG.nc", # the file name for our full kriging output
  Dir = Dir.Exports # which directory to save our final input in
)
```

Figure 8. Run KrigR in R.

The degree of localisation describes the number of neighbouring grid cells used to derive the relationships between the field to be downscaled and the co-variates. When changing the degree of localisation, computational cost must be considered. If the defined degree of localisation is too small, then the output will not be accurate enough (large standard errors, i.e. large confidence intervals on the estimates). On the other hand, defining the degree of localisation too large will mean that computational resources becomes a concern, as the cost becomes exponentially more expensive. [8]

Kriging in Python

To perform kriging using Python, you can use the pykrige library. Here's an example of kriging interpolation for temperature data:


```

datum = 'WGS84' # EPSG code: 4326
projection = 'EPSG:32610' # UTM Zone 10N

transformer = pyproj.Transformer.from_crs(datum, projection, always_xy=True)

datat = xr.open_dataset(r"C:\Users\DoctorMalatji\Downloads\area1.nc")## ensemble

# Extract the relevant variables (Longitude, latitude, u-component, and v-component of wind)
lon = datat.longitude.values
lat = datat.latitude.values
t=datat.t2m[0].values ## temperature
new_lon = np.linspace(lon.min(), lon.max(), 2262) # Adjust the number of points as needed
new_lat = np.linspace(lat.min(), lat.max(), 2262)

new_lon_grid, new_lat_grid = np.meshgrid(new_lon, new_lat)

points1 = np.array([(xi, yi) for xi in lon for yi in lat])
grid_points = np.column_stack((lon.ravel(), lat.ravel()))
new_grid_points = np.column_stack((new_lon_grid.ravel(), new_lat_grid.ravel()))

t1=t.ravel()
kriging_model = OrdinaryKriging(points1[:, 0],points1[:, 1],t1[::-1], variogram_model='spherical', verbose=False)
z, ss = kriging_model.execute('grid', new_lon, new_lat)
    
```

Figure 9. Kriging code in python (z is the downscaled data).

Figure 10. (a) Downloaded ERA5 data and the (b) downscaled data.

5. Calculating variables for Atlite

Atlite is a Python library for converting weather data (like wind speeds, solar influx) into energy systems data. It is designed to keep computing resource requirements (CPU, RAM) usage low. It is therefore well suited to be used with big weather datasets.

Atlite can process climate data variables and can convert them into power-system relevant time series for any subsets of a full weather database. However, the interpolated ERA5 variables (also called “downscaled data” in the previous section) must be converted into the correct format and/or variable for use in Atlite. In the figure below the mapping of the ERA5 variables to the variables required by Atlite is shown.

Figure 11. ERA5 and Atlite variables relationship.

The calculations required to convert the ERA5 data to the required Atlite variables are discussed below.

i. Time

The time variable is left unchanged since the metadata is needed for the next step when the Atlite variables are added to a NetCDF file.

ii. Height

The height variable is computed by dividing the given height data (z) by the acceleration due to gravity (g_0). This represents the geopotential height.

$$\text{height} = \frac{z}{g_0}$$

iii. Wind Speed

The variable $wnd100m$ represents the wind speed at 100 meters above the surface. It's calculated by taking the square root of the sum of the squared eastward wind component (u_{100}) and the squared northward wind component (v_{100}).

$$wnd100m = \sqrt{u_{100}^2 + v_{100}^2}$$

iv. Wind Azimuth and Adjusted Wind Azimuth

The azimuth variable represents the wind direction angle from the north. It's calculated using the arctangent function applied to the eastward and northward wind components.

$$\text{wind azimuth} = \tan^{-1} 2(u_{100}, v_{100})$$

To ensure wind azimuth angles are within the range of $([0, 2\pi])$, this step adjusts the azimuth angle. If the azimuth is negative, (2π) is added to it; otherwise, it remains unchanged.

$$\text{adjusted wind azimuth} = \begin{cases} \text{wind azimuth} + 2\pi, & \text{azimuth} \geq 0 \\ \text{wind azimuth}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

v. Roughness

The roughness variable represents the surface roughness. It is set to a constant value (2×10^{-4}) if the surface roughness data (fsr) is greater than or equal to 0.0; otherwise, it takes the value of (fsr).

$$\text{roughness} = \begin{cases} 2 \times 10^{-4}, & fsr \geq 0.0 \\ fsr, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

vi. Influx Direct and Influx TOA

The influx direct and influx toa variables represent incoming direct and total solar radiation per second, respectively. The values are obtained by dividing the corresponding solar radiation values (f_{dir}) and (t_{isr}) by 60×60 to convert from per hour to per second. If the total the corresponding solar radiation values are less than 0, set influx toa and direct values to 0.

Kommentiert [NB2]: @Toshka Coleman should we maybe switch the paragraph and equation around? So that the text acts like a little introduction? What do you think?

Kommentiert [TC3R2]: Yes will do!

$$\text{influx toa} = \begin{cases} \frac{t_{\text{isr}}}{60 \times 60}, & \text{influx toa} \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{influx toa} < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{influx direct} = \begin{cases} \frac{f_{\text{dir}}}{60 \times 60}, & \text{influx direct} \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{influx direct} < 0 \end{cases}$$

vii. Albedo

The albedo variable represents the surface reflectivity. It's calculated as the ratio of the difference between total downward and reflected solar radiation to total downward solar radiation. If total downward solar radiation (ssrd) is zero, albedo is set to 0.

$$\text{albedo} = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ssrd} - \text{ssr}}{\text{ssrd}}, & \text{ssrd} \neq 0 \\ 0, & \text{ssrd} = 0 \end{cases}$$

viii. Influx Diffuse Calculation

The influx diffuse variable represents incoming diffuse solar radiation per second. It's computed by subtracting direct solar radiation (f_{dir}) from total downward solar radiation (ssrd), and then dividing by 60×60 . It's set to 0 if influx diffuse is negative.

$$\text{influx diffuse} = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ssrd} - f_{\text{dir}}}{60 \times 60}, & \text{influx diffuse} \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{influx diffuse} < 0 \end{cases}$$

ix. Temperature and Soil Temperature

The temperature (2t) and soil temperature (stl4) variables represent air and soil temperatures, respectively.

$$\text{temperature} = 2t$$

$$\text{soil temperature} = \text{stl4}$$

x. Runoff

The runoff variable represents runoff data. It's set to the value of ro if ro is positive; otherwise, it's set to 0.

$$\text{runoff} = \begin{cases} ro, & ro \geq 0 \\ 0, & ro < 0 \end{cases}$$

xi. Solar Altitude and Azimuth

Solar altitude and azimuth are calculated using the *pvl* package. The *pvl* python function takes the time, latitude and longitude to calculate the solar altitude and azimuth for each pixel.

Kommentiert [TC4]: @Nicolene Botha Should I add "max" for all the calculations that are clipped at 0? Also should I use the first or second notation?

Kommentiert [NB5R4]: Second notation is probably clearer and more familiar to most readers

Kommentiert [NB6R4]: I think it should be used where it makes sense for you.

Kommentiert [TC7R4]: Okay sure, thank you!

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Solar positions are calculated for a grid of latitudes and longitudes across the timestamps, and the results are stored. This process includes creating latitude and longitude grids, flattening arrays for vectorized calculations, using `pvlib.solarposition.get_solarposition` for simultaneous calculations, and reshaping the results to match the original grid shape.

As per a report by Reda and Andreas (2004), the `pvlib` calculations for solar altitude (α) and azimuth (A) are calculated by using the observer's latitude (φ), Solar Declination (δ), and Solar Hour Angle (H).

$$\text{solar altitude } (\alpha) = \sin^{-1}(\sin(\varphi) * \sin(\delta) + \cos(\varphi) * \cos(\delta) * \cos(H))$$

$$\text{solar azimuth } (A) = \cos^{-1}((\sin(\delta) - \sin(\alpha) * \sin(\varphi)) / (\cos(\alpha) * \cos(\varphi)))$$

xii. x and y

x (set equal to the longitude) and y (set equal to the latitude) should be created as well. These are needed for the solar calculations in `Atlite`.

6. Create NETCDF file

The newly calculated variables are added into a NetCDF file, together with the original time variable.

In the example below, each variable is not defined, but an example of each variable type is shown.

```
import netCDF4 as nc
import numpy as np

ds = nc.Dataset(filename, 'w', format='NETCDF4')

## Create Global Attributes
ds.title = 'Interpolated'
ds.Conventions = 'CF-1.6'
ds.prepared_features = ['height', 'runoff', 'temperature', 'wind', 'influx']
ds.module = 'era5'

## Create Dimensions
y_dim = ds.createDimension('y', len(lat))
lon_dim = ds.createDimension('lon', len(lon))
time_dim = ds.createDimension('time', len(time))

## Create Variables
y_var = ds.createVariable('y', np.float64, ('y',))
y_var.units = 'meters'
y_var[:] = lat

time_var = ds.createVariable('time', 'f4', ('time',))
time_var.standard_name = 'time'
time_var.time_step = 'hourly'
time_var.calendar = time.calendar
time_var.axis = 'T'
time_var.units = time.units
time_var[:] = time

crs_var = ds.createVariable('crs', np.int8, ())
crs_var.standard_name = 'crs'
crs_var.grid_mapping_name = 'y_x'
crs_var.crs_wkt = ("GEOGCS['GCS_WGS_1984', DATUM['D_WGS_1984',
    'SPHEROID['WGS_1984', 6378137.0, 298.257223563]],
    'PRIMEM['Greenwich', 0, 0],
    'UNIT['Degree', 0.0174532925199433]]")

height_var = ds.createVariable('height', np.float64, ('y', 'x'), fill_value=9999)
height_var.units = 'meters'
height_var.grid_mapping = 'crs'
height_var[:, :] = height ## dimation = (y, x)

wnd100m_var = ds.createVariable('wnd100m', np.float64, ('time', 'y', 'x'), fill_value=9999)
wnd100m_var.units = 'm/s'
wnd100m_var.grid_mapping = 'crs'
wnd100m_var[:, :, :] = wnd100m ## dimation = (time, y, x)

ds.close()
```

Under "Create Dimensions", the 'x_dim' and 'lat_dim' should also be created. Similarly, under "Create Variable"

- x_var
- lat_var and
- lon_var

should be defined in the same way as the y_var, while

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- wnd_azimuth_var,
- roughness_var,
- influx_toa_var,
- influx_direct_var,
- influx_diffuse_var,
- albedo_var,
- temperature_var,
- soil_temperature_var,
- runoff_var,
- solar_altitude_var and
- solar_azimuth_var

should be defined in the same way as 'wnd100_var' since these variables have the same dimension of (time, latitude, longitude) or (time, y, x).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

7. Calculate Power Generation using Atlite

The newly created NetCDF file is read by Atlite using the Cutout package.

```
import atlite
cutout = atlite.Cutout("NetCDF_file_path")
```

7.1 Specifying the area

Apart from the larger area that is downloaded (section 3) and downscaled (section 4), a smaller area of interest can be specified for renewable installation by providing the latitude and longitude of one or more pixels. In the case of a larger area, a polygon can be provided.

There are 3 ways to specify the area where the renewables are installed.

i. Specific sites

One or more sites can be specified using latitude and longitude by adding the site name, latitude and longitude and the corresponding installed capacity into a list and converted into a GeoDataFrame.

If the user does not provide a location, the capacity factors (discussed below in subsection 7.4) can be used to identify the locations (pixels) with the largest power generation potential.

```
capacities = [10,30]
site = [
    ["site 1", -30.562349, 20.133051, capacities[0]],
    ["site 2", -30.955298, 19.571255, capacities[1]],
]
```

```
sites = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    site,
    columns=["name", "x", "y", "capacity"],
    ).set_index("name")
```

The x and y values in the Atlite cutout closest to the site's latitudes and longitudes are identified.

```
nearest = cutout.data.sel({"x": sites.x.values, "y": sites.y.values}, "nearest").coords
sites["x"] = nearest.get("x").values
sites["y"] = nearest.get("y").values
```

The time series power generation function in Atlite for solar PV and wind requires a DataFrame containing the coordinates, capacity and geometry (see below) as well as the layout, as input.

```
cells = cutout.grid
cells_generation = sites.merge(cells, how="inner").rename(pd.Series(sites.index))
```

cells_generation - DataFrame

index	x	y	capacity	geometry
site 1	-30.5	20.25	10	POLYGON ((-30.375 20.125, -30.375 20.375, -30.625 20.375, -30.625 20.125, -30.375 20.125))
site 2	-31	19.5	30	POLYGON ((-30.875 19.375, -30.875 19.625, -31.125 19.625, -31.125 19.375, -30.875 19.375))

The layout can be generated using the python XArray function generating a core.DataArray containing the *cells_generation* DataFrame and capacity factor map for re-indexing, calculated in subsection 4.

```
layout = (
    xr.DataArray(cells_generation.set_index(["y", "x"]).capacity.unstack())
    .reindex_like(cap_map)
    .rename("Installed Capacity [MW]")
)
```

As a result, all the pixels not of interest are set to NaN and the only pixels with non-NaN values are the pixels of interest with the corresponding installed capacity as the values.

The layout is combined with a shape, when eventually calculating the power. In this scenario, where individual sites are selected, the shape would be set as *cells_generation.geometry*. This sets the shape equal to each individual polygon defining each site (or pixel).

```
In [11]: cells_generation.geometry
Out[11]:
site 1 POLYGON ((-30.37500 20.12500, -30.37500 20.375...
site 2 POLYGON ((-30.87500 19.37500, -30.87500 19.625...
Name: geometry, dtype: geometry
```

Below is an example of how the layout would look when combined with the shape and the resulting power generation curves.

Figure 12. (a) Layout and shape when defining specific sites (pixels) and (b) the resulting power generation curves for the specified areas.

In this example random pixels were selected with 10MW installed at site 1 and 30MW installed at site 2.

ii. Aggregating sites within a polygon

If the selected sites fall within a specific polygon the generated power of each site falling within the polygon can be aggregated. This is done by setting all the missing values to zero and setting the shape equal to the polygon.

Kommentiert [GW8]: Caption required

```
layout_agg = copy.deepcopy(layout)
layout_ag = layout_agg.fillna(0)
power_generation_agg = (
    cutout.wind("Vestas_V112_3MW", layout=layout_ag, shapes=polygon)
    .to_pandas()
    .rename_axis(index="", columns="shapes")
)
```

Below is an example of how the layout would look when combined with the shape (polygon) and the resulting power generation curve.

Figure 13. (a) Layout and shape when aggregating sites within a specified polygon and (b) the resulting aggregated power generation curve for the polygon.

In this example site 1 falls inside the polygon and site 2 falls outside the polygon. This means that site 2 is not used in the calculation of the aggregated power. If site 2 fell inside the polygon, the aggregated power generation would be equal to the sum of sites 1 and 2, instead it's now just equal to site 1 in the top example.

If a multipolygon is provided, a separate curve would show the aggregated power within each polygon in separate graphs.

iii. Average within a polygon

If the user wants to determine the average projected power generation for a specific capacity value installed in a polygon, but sites are not specified, the user can determine the number of pixels within the polygon and calculate the average capacity per pixel. By setting each pixel within the polygon equal to the calculated capacity per pixel; setting all missing values equal to zero; and setting the shape equal to the polygon, the average power generation for the installed capacity within the whole area (polygon) can be determined.

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```
## make copy of layout
uniform = copy.deepcopy(layout_ag)
## set all pixels inside the polygon to 1
ar = masked_array*0+1
## set new layout equal to masked array
uniform.data = ar

## count all pixels which are not nan
## (this is used to determine the number of pixels with the polygon)
num_pix = np.nansum(ar)

installed_capacity = np.sum(capacities) #MW

## Create an uniform layout
uniform = uniform*(installed_capacity / num_pix)
power_generation_mean = (
    cutout.wind("Vestas_V112_3MW", layout=uniform.fillna(0), shapes=polygon)
    .to_pandas()
    .rename_axis(index="", columns="shapes")
)
```

Below is an example of how the layout would look when combined with the shape (polygon) and the resulting power generation curve.

Figure 14. (a) Layout and shape when averaging the installed capacity over each pixel within the specified polygon and (b) the resulting total power generation curve for the polygon.

In this example the total installed capacity of 40MW (10+30 MW) is averaged over all the pixels inside the polygon. This total average power generation will not be equal to exactly site 1 + site 2 since this is spread out over multiple pixels. The reason the power generation trend looks similar to the above trends is because this is done over a relatively small area and the spatial variation is minimal.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

Kommentiert [GW9]: Caption required

7.2 Specifying the wind turbine

The Atlite Python package has with several built-in wind turbine specifications which can be obtained with the command:

```
turb_lst = ]
for tur in atlite.windturbines:
    turb_lst.append(tur)
print(turb_lst)
```

A built-in turbine can be selected by setting "turbine" equal to the name of one of the listed turbines, e.g., turbine = 'Vestas_V90_3MW'

A custom turbine (not in the current list) can be used by either specifying the power of wind (POW) value, velocity, P and hub height in a dictionary, or by specifying the POW, velocity and hub height in a yaml file.

Dictionary example:

```
POW = np.array(0.000, 0.000, 0.005, 0.150, 0.300, 0.525, 0.905, 1.375, 1.950, 2.580, 2.960, 3.050,
               3.060, 3.060, 0.000))
velocity = np.array(0, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 25, 25])
turbine = {"hub_height":99, "V": velocity, "POW": POW, "P": np.max(POW)}
```

An example of a yaml file defining a custom turbine is shown below.

```
# SPDX-FileCopyrightText: 2023 CSIR
#
# SPDX-License-Identifier: CC-BY-4.0

# Turbine characteristic data
name: E101 3000 kW
# The manufacturer of this turbine
manufacturer: Enercon
# Link to the original datasheet of the turbine
source: http://www.enercon.de/p/downloads/EN_Productoverview_0710.pdf

# Hub height in meters
HUB_HEIGHT: 99
# Power curve, specified as lists of velocities and powers, including
# cut-in and cut-out speeds
# Power curve velocities in m/s
V: [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 28, 28]
# Generated power from the power curves in MW
POW: [0.000, 0.000, 0.003, 0.037, 0.118, 0.258, 0.479, 0.790, 1.200, 1.710, 2.340, 2.867, 3.034, 3.050, 3.050, 0.000]
```

If a yaml file is used, the file must be read by the Atlite resource function.

```
turbine = atlite.resource.get_windturbineconfig(Path("wind_yaml_path"))
```

7.3 Specifying the solar panel

There are also solar panels built into Atlite which can be viewed using the `atlite.solarpanels` function similar to the `atlite.windturbines` function in the previous section.

e.g., panel = "CSi"

Custom panels can be incorporated using a yaml file and the file is read using the function:

```
panel = atlite.resource.get_solarpanelconfig(Path("solar_yaml_path"))
```


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There are 2 yaml templates that can be used.

Template 1:

```
# SPDX-FileCopyrightText: 2021 The Atlite Authors
#
# SPDX-License-Identifier: CC-BY-4.0

model: huld
name: CSi
source: Huld 2010

# Used for calculating capacity per m2
efficiency: 0.1

# Panel temperature coefficient of ambient temperature
c_temp_amb: 1
# Panel temperature coefficient of irradiance
c_temp_irrad: 0.035 # 0.035 K / (W/m2)

# Reference conditions
r_tamb: 293 # 20 degC
r_tmod: 298 # 25 degC
r_irradiance: 1000 # W/m^2

# Fitting parameters
k_1: -0.017162
k_2: -0.040289
k_3: -0.004681
k_4: 0.000148
k_5: 0.000169
k_6: 0.000005

inverter_efficiency: 0.9
```

Figure 15. Solar panel template 1

Template 2:

```

# SPDX-FileCopyrightText: 2021 The Atlite Authors
#
# SPDX-License-Identifier: CC-BY-4.0

model: bofinger

# Solar panel data
name: Kaneka Hybrid
# The manufacturer of this panel
manufacturer: Kaneka
# Link to the original datasheet of the panel
source: http://www.kaneka-solar.com/products/pdf/U-EA.pdf

# Solar radiation below which the panel stops giving useful power
threshold: 1

# Area of the solar panel in m^2
area: 1.22
# Rated production in watt peak
rated_production: 89.3

# A, B, C are coefficients for the equation : efficiency = A + B*I + C*logI and
# are calculated by using the three different values of solar
# radiation and their peak powers at 25deg C module temperature for
# corresponding radiations from the data sheet
# That model comes from
A: 0.0659164166836276
B: -4.44310393547042E-06
C: 0.0122044905275824

#temperature power coefficient given in data sheet
D: -0.0035

#Nominal Operating Cell Temperature given in data sheet
NOCT: 318
#STC (Standard testing Condition) module temperature in K
Tstd: 298
#NTC (Nomial testing Condition) ambient temperature in K
Tamb: 293
#NTC radiation in W/m2
Intc: 800
#Transmittance times absorptance for glass panel in front of solar cell
ta: 0.9

inverter_efficiency: 0.9

```

Figure 16. Solar panel template 2

7.4 Capacity factors

7.4.1 Average Capacity factor

The Capacity factors for each pixel in the area of interest for a custom turbine or solar panel is calculated using the Atlite *cutout.wind* or *cutout.pv* functions. This capacity factor map gives the average for each pixel over the whole time period.

```
cap_factors = cutout.wind(turbine = turbine, capacity_factor=True)
```

```
cap_factors = cutout.pv(panel = p, orientation = {"slope":0,"azimuth":0.0}, capacity_factor=True)
```


Figure 17. Capacity factors for (left) a custom wind turbine and (right) custom solar panel over the whole area.

7.4.2 Hourly capacity factor maps

The user may want the capacity factors maps hourly for the whole period instead of the average capacity for that period.

The NetCDF file containing all the calculated variables is broken into hourly timesteps so that each time step is a separate file. These hourly NetCDF files are used with the Atlite functions in subsection 7.4.1 to calculate the hourly capacity factor maps for the selected technology.

7.5 Power Generation

Potential power generation over time for the selected sites are calculated using the *cutout.wind* or *cutout.pv* functions.

```
power_generation = cutout.wind(turbine, layout=layout, shapes=cells_generation.geometry)
```

In the figure below the wind at the 2 selected sites are displayed on the left and the corresponding potential generated wind power is shown on the right with set capacities of 20 and 30 MW respectively.

Figure 18. (Left) Wind and (right) corresponding power generation, for a custom wind turbine at 2 sites

The solar power generation calculation requires the same inputs as the wind but requires the panel orientation as well.

```
power_generation = cutout.pv(panel=solar, orientation={"slope":0,"azimuth":0.0}, layout=layout,
shapes=calls_generation.geometry)
```

The optimal orientation in Atlite is defined as "slope" = 0 and "azimuth" = 0.0.

Figure 19. Potential solar power generation at 3 different sites using a custom panel.

7.6 Test output with different turbines and panels

The potential power generation at a site using different wind turbines and solar panels, built into Atlite, is calculated to see the influence of the wind turbine and solar panel attributes on the calculation.

The selected date is 01 Dec 2019 with the time window 00:00 – 23:00.

Site 1 is located at [18.25, -33.75] with 25 MW installed wind capacity.

Figure 20. Potential wind power generation for different wind turbines at the same site, time and installed capacity

Site 2 is at location [18.75, -33.25] with 10 MW installed solar capacity.

Figure 21. Potential wind power generation for different solar panels at the same site, time and installed capacity

7.7 Different installed capacity

The built in Vestas_V90_3MW turbine and CSi solar panel technologies are selected and the power generation for different installed capacities are compared at the same area and time.

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Figure 22. Potential power generation calculated using different installed capacity for (a) wind and (b) solar.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

7.8 Speed test

After the data download and variable interpolation, the Atlite variable calculations is the next most computationally expensive task. Due to this, a speed test was conducted on the variable calculations for different time periods and area sizes. The results of the test runs are provided below.

Time period (hour)	Area size (number of pixels)	Total number of data points	Run time (seconds)
24	25	600	1.39
48	25	1 200	3.14
72	25	1 800	4.3
168 (1 week)	25 (5x5)	4 200	9.72
720 (1 month)	25	18 000	52.78
1440 (2 months)	25	36 600	87.6 (1.46 minutes)
4416 (6 months)	25	110 400	274.8 (4.58 minutes)
168 (1 week)	49 (7x7)	8 232	26.09
168	81 (9x9)	13 608	46.87
168	289 (17x17)	48 552	149.4 (2.49 minutes)
168	441 (21x21)	74 088	181.2 (3.02 minutes)
168	625 (25x25)	105 000	262.8 (4.38 minutes)
168	1681 (41x41)	282 408	707.4 (11.79 minutes)

Table 2. Speed test for calculation.

As opposed to the data download speed tests, larger areas versus longer time periods do not have large influence on the calculation time. The calculation time value is mostly dependent on the total number of pixels.

8. LEAP-RE project OASES workflow to process wind power data

8.1 Power Timeseries and Capacity Factor Estimation using Atlite

This section outlines the methodology and system setup for generating power time series and calculating capacity factors using the Atlite framework. The tool automates the retrieval of meteorological reanalysis data from the ERA5 dataset and processes it to produce site-specific renewable energy generation estimates as described in the previous sections. Note that this WP links WP3 and WP4 in the overall project.

8.1.1 System Requirements and Setup

To utilize the ERA5 data via the cdsapi Python package, valid access credentials from the Climate Data Store (CDS) are required. These credentials must be stored in a .cdsapirc configuration file. On Windows systems, due to naming limitations with leading dots in filenames, a template file named sample_cdsapirc.txt is provided as a work around. Users must copy and rename this file to cdsapirc.txt and input their personalized credentials as obtained from the CDS website.

Users are then required to customize the input parameters in the script located at: src/user_input.py. This script defines various configuration options including site coordinates, date ranges, and system-specific parameters such as interpolation resolution, turbine and solar panel configuration files, and capacity assumptions.

8.1.2 Execution Methods

The package supports Docker and command line execution modes for flexibility and automation.

To initiate the full pipeline using Docker, the following command should be executed from the root of the project directory:

```
docker-compose up -d
```

For direct execution without Docker, the main processing script can be run manually after setting up the Python environment using the requirements.txt file:

```
python power_generation_timeseries_v1.py
```

Alternatively, the script supports command-line arguments to allow fine-tuned control over input parameters. Below is an example of a fully parameterized execution:

```
python power_generation_timeseries_v1.py
--FILENAME '["output_temp"]'
--COORD_LST '[[[27.5, -25.5], [28.5, -25.5], [28.5, -26.5], [27.5, -26.5]]]'
--DATE '{"year": "2022", "month": "8", "day": ["01", ..., "31"]}'
--TIME '["00:00", "01:00", ..., "23:00"]'
--AREA_FLAG 3
```


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```
--SITE_LIST_WIND                '[']
--SITE_LIST_SOLAR                '[']
--LOC                            '[-29.15,19.0,-31.0,21.1]'
--TURBINE_FLAG                    0
--TURBINE_FILE_NAME              custom_turbine_and_panel/Test_Turbine.yaml
--SOLAR_FILE_TYPE                1
--SOLAR_FILE_NAME                CSi
--ORIENTATION                    latitude_optimal
--C_WIND                         '[50]'
--C_PV                           '[50]'
--INTERP                         True
--INTERP_RES                     0.045
--CAP_FAC_TIME                   True
--PLOTING False
```

Once run, the codes will:

1. Download the required ERA5 data,
2. Process the data to derive power generation timeseries,
3. And lastly compute the capacity factors.

8.1.3 Output

Upon successful execution, the tool outputs hourly power generation timeseries, and capacity factors over the specified period and spatial region.

These results are used in the following package for generating the IRENA Flextool capacity factor tiers.

8.2 Tier Selection and Preprocessing Toolbox for IRENA-Flextool

This toolbox provides a modular framework to generate spatial and temporal "tiers" based on capacity factor data from the previous sections output and/or the Global Wind Atlas. These tiers are designed to feed into the IRENA Flextool, enabling spatially resolved renewable energy modelling scenarios.

The system is structured to support:

1. Data preprocessing from large, gridded datasets (NetCDF).
2. Spatial tier delineation via percentile bounds, geospatial user-defined inputs, or hybrid correction models.
3. Time series generation from gridded data via aggregation, spatial filtering, and tier-based selection logic.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

8.2.1 Tiering Options and outputs

The codebase supports seven tier generation methodologies, all of which conform to the same architectural principle:

1. geospatial filtering
2. temporal aggregation
3. tier reduction
4. lastly, the time series export.

8.2.2 Code execution

Note that to run the codes, there are different options available:

1. Docker. Parameters and variables can be set in the .env file.
2. On the command line interface. The individual command line parameters are described in the git repository.
3. Stand-alone using user_input_template.py. This is a wrapper file for running the different tier options. Input data are set using the OPTION parameter as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5_1, 5_2, 6_1, 6_2 or 7. Other specific variables are set in the file itself.

Option		Tiering Description	Scripts	Inputs	Output	Interactivity
1		Top % capacity factors (upper % limit)	Option_1_upper_percentage_atlite.py	Atlite average CF	Timeseries per tier CSV	CLI + Docker
2		Top % capacity (upper % limit) using WAD data → matched to Atlite location	Option_2_upper_percentage_WAD.py	WAD (spatial) → Atlite (temporal)	Timeseries per tier CSV	CLI + Docker + Web Browser
3		Five different bounded % timeseries averaged into a single CF series	Option_3_bound_percentage_atlite.py	Atlite	Timeseries per tier CSV	CLI + Docker
4		Same as Option 3 but using WAD data.	Option_4_bound_percentage_WAD.py	WAD (spatial) → Atlite (temporal)	Timeseries per tier CSV	CLI + Docker
5		User-defined geometries giving a single CF series per geometry.	Option_5_step1_geometry_selection.py and Option_5_step2_tier_generation_average_per_geometry.py	Atlite	Timeseries per geometry CSV	CLI + Docker + Web Browser

Option		Tiering Description	Scripts	Inputs	Output	Interactivity
6		Same as Option 5 but multiple tiers per geometry based on the five different percentage bounds. I.e. up to 5 different tiers per geometry.	Option_6_step1_geometry_selection.py and Option_6_step2_tier_generation_bounds_per_geometry.py	Atlite	Timeseries per geometry CSV	CLI + Docker + Web Browser
7		User defined scaled tier using WAD data. I.e. Custom correction function	Option_7_WAD_Atlite_correction_user_defined.py	WAD + Atlite	User scaled tiers CSV	CLI + Docker

Table 3. Tiering Options for the capacity factors.

8.2.3 Assumptions and notes

1. For points geometry selection, the nearest timeseries datapoint in the available dataset is found and selected.
2. Note that the code is sensitive to NaN and missing values. Ensure datasets do not have NaN or missing values.
3. Option 1, 2, 3, 4 and 7 do not require user input on a browser. Options 5 and 6 require the user input on a browser.
4. All relevant Python packages are found in requirements.txt file.
5. If using Docker, copy the sample.env to an .env file and use this file instead. The .env file contains all user settings needed for running the codes.
6. Do not change the assets folder unless it is required.
7. For Options 5 and 6, too high a resolution for the world atlas NetCDF data will significantly increase the rendering time on the browser.
8. Only single band (not classified) .tif files used as masks, make sure they each have an extent. The user can add as many as they want in the masks folder. A method is described in this git repository and in the below sections on how to convert a classified raster to a single band raster.
9. Step 1 for Option 5 and 6 requires time to load on the map in the web browser, due to reading the mask files. Python's Dash module initially loads the data twice to ensure the cache is fulfilled, which requires time.
10. The scripts for step 2 in Options 5 and 6, has a variable, OPTION_5_VIEW_VALID_GEOMETRIES and OPTION_6_VIEW_VALID_GEOMETRIES respectively, which enables the user to visualize the map and geometries in the web browser.
11. The link to the web browser page is shown in the console output as per example of this picture below

```
Visualization starting up ...
Dash is running on http://127.0.0.1:8050/

* Serving Flask app 'Option_6_step2_tier_generation_bounds_per_geometry' (lazy loading)
* Environment: production
  WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.
  Use a production WSGI server instead.
* Debug mode: on
```

Figure 23. Python's Dash development server running the tier generation codes for Option 5 and 6.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

8.2.4 Preprocessing the Wind Atlas Data

Before using the Wind Atlas data (netcdf file), it needs to be downloaded from <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/download/gis-files> and saved to the assets folder. See image below:

Figure 24. Global Wind Atlas Data (WAD) Download.

Gdal or QGIS is needed to process the wind atlas data from tif to netcdf format.

In gdal:

1. Convert your tif file into a proper geotif file with a 2-dimensional layer using:
 - a. `gdal_translate -b 1 -of GTiff D:\tempDownloads\ZAF_capacity-factor_IEC1.tif D:\tempDownloads\temp.tif`
2. Translate the file into a netcdf file:
 - a. `gdal_translate -of NetCDF -co "FORMAT=NC4" -a_nodata nan -a_srs EPSG:4326 -mo "Minimum=0.0185328294" -mo "Maximum=0.6504413486" D:\tempDownloads\temp.tif D:\tempDownloads\output.nc`

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In QGIS, open the python console (Plugins --> Python Console) and run the following commands:

```
1. import os
2. from osgeo import gdal
3. input_tif = '/path/to/input.tif'
4. temp_tif = '/path/to/temp.tif'
5. output_nc = '/path/to/output.nc'
6. input_ds = gdal.Open(input_tif)
7. band = input_ds.GetRasterBand(1)
8. array = band.ReadAsArray()
9. cols = input_ds.RasterXSize
10. rows = input_ds.RasterYSize
11. driver = gdal.GetDriverByName('GTiff')
12. output_ds = driver.Create(temp_tif, cols, rows, 1, band.DataType)
13. output_ds.GetRasterBand(1).WriteArray(array)
14. output_ds.SetGeoTransform(input_ds.GetGeoTransform())
15. output_ds.SetProjection(input_ds.GetProjection())
16. output_ds = None
17. input_ds = None
18. gdal.Translate(output_nc, temp_tif, format='NetCDF',
    outputSRS='EPSG:4326',creationOptions=['FORMAT=NC4'])
19. os.remove(temp_tif)
```

8.2.5 Preparing the Wind Atlas Data PNG file

To get the png picture that is required for the web browser, use QGIS:

1. style the map accordingly
2. click project then import/export
3. finally export map to png image.

Select appropriate bounds for the image (found in the .env file) so that it fits on the South African border on the web browser.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 963530.

8.2.6 User masks preparation

As noted in the above sections, only single band (not classified) .tif files can be used as masks. The user must ensure the .tif files each have an extent. All mask files should be added to the masks folder. The method below is also described in the git repository readme on how to convert a classified raster to a single band raster.

Use QGIS load the classified tiff layer.

Figure 25. QGIS Layer preview with style for mask tif file.

Open the raster calculator (selecting raster then raster calculator) and perform the calculation "classified_raster_band@1" * 1.

Save the result to a new tif file. Use this new single band tiff file as your mask in the assets/masks folder.

Figure 26. QGIS Raster calculation for generating single band tif mask file.

Please remove all classified masks (or rename the extension) from the assets/masks folder so that it does not load them, this is to save run time.

9. Code repositories

All code repositories can be found on Github. The main repository is VTT's repository as it is used for integration into IRENA Flextool:

https://github.com/vttresearch/OASES_wind_power_data.git

The following two repositories are embedded into the main repository but contain the modules described in the above two sections:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15363899>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15363917>

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10. Final remarks

This report provides a description of the methodology and software code used for downscaling of climate data from open access publicly available (large scale) climate data and projections to a local scale, and to translate these into a time series of renewable energy generated at the local area. The intention is that the report will serve as a type of manual for using the developed methods, which can be tested and refined for use in energy scenario modelling.

The final step in Work Package 3 is then to end off with deliverable D3.3: *Description of the time series data sets for wind and solar generation for the selected national case studies of Egypt, Algeria and South Africa.*

Bibliography

- [1] Q. Guo, Y. Su and T. Hu, "Chapter 6 - LiDAR Data Filtering and Digital Elevation Model Generation," in *LiDAR Principles, Processing and Applications in Forest Ecology*, Academic Press, 2023, pp. 171-214.
- [2] E. Kusch and R. Davy, "KrigR—a tool for downloading and statistically downscaling climate reanalysis data," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 17, no. 2, p. 024005, 2022.
- [3] Copernicus, "Welcome to the Climate Data Store," Copernicus Climate Change Service, [Online]. Available: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>. [Accessed 2023 9 1].
- [4] H. Chen, "Chapter 3 - Techniques of fine reservoir description," in *Fine Reservoir Description*, Gulf Professional Publishing, 2022, pp. 113-348.
- [5] J. J. Danielson and D. B. Gesch, "Global multi-resolution terrain elevation data 2010 (GMTED2010)," 2011.
- [6] C. Daly, W. P. Gibson, G. H. Taylor, G. L. Johnson and P. Pasteris, "A knowledge-based approach to the statistical mapping of climate," *Climate research*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 99-113, 2002.
- [7] P. H. Hiemstra, E. J. Pebesma, C. J. Twenhöfel and G. B. Heuvelink, "Real-time automatic interpolation of ambient gamma dose rates from the Dutch radioactivity monitoring network," *Computers & Geosciences*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 1711-1721, 2009.
- [8] R. Davy and E. Kusch, "Reconciling high resolution climate datasets using KrigR," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 16, no. 12, p. 124040, 2021.
- [9] N. Mohamudally, *Time Series and Renewable Energy Forecasting*, online publication: IntechOpen, 2018.

- [10 University of New Mexico, "AR, MA and ARMA models," 17 9 2006. [Online].
] Available: https://www.math.unm.edu/~ghuerta/tseries/week4_1.pdf.
- [11 R. Inman, H. Pedro and C. Coimbra, "Solar forecasting methods for
] renewable energy integration," *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, pp. 39:535-576, 2013.
- [12 W. Wang and Z. Niu, "Time series analysis of NASDAQ composite based on
] seasonal ARIMA," in *Proceeding of the International Conference on Management and Service Science*, Wuhan, 2009.
- [13 J. Contreas-Reyes and W. Palma, "Statistical analysis of autoregressive
] fractionally integrated," *Computational Statistics*, pp. 28(5):2309-2331, 2013.
- [14 A. Hatemi, "Multivariate tests for autocorrelation in the stable and unstable
] VAR models," *Economic Modelling*, pp. 21(4):661-683, 2004.
- [15 R. Engle, "Autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity with estimates of
] the variance of United Kingdom inflation," *Econometrica*, pp. 50(4):987-1007, 1982.
- [16 S. Pfenninger, "Dealing with multiple decades of hourly wind and PV time
] series in energy models: A comparison of methods to reduce time resolution and the planning implications of inter-annual variability," *Applied Energy*, pp. 197:1-13, 2017.
- [17 Weston.pace, "k-means clustering," 26 July 2007. [Online]. Available:
] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/K-means_clustering.
- [18 CarbonPlan, "Open data and tools for multiple methods of global climate
] downscaling," 30 June 2022. [Online]. Available:
<https://carbonplan.org/research/cmip6-downscaling-explainer>.
- [19 Climatology Lab, "MACA," 1 November 2022. [Online]. Available:
] <https://www.climatologylab.org/maca.html>.
- [20 Cornell University, "DeepSD: Generating High Resolution Climate Change
] Projections through Single Image Super-Resolution," 9 March 2017.
[Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.03126>.
- [21 M. P. Clark and L. E. Hay, "Use of medium-range numerical weather
] prediction model output to produce forecasts of streamflow," *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, pp. 5(1), 15-32, 2004.
- [22 M. P. Clark and A. G. Slater, "Probabilistic quantitative precipitation
] estimation in complex terrain," *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, pp. 7(1), 3-22, 2006.
- [23 R. L. Wilby, J. Troni, Y. Biot, L. Tedd, B. C. Hewitson, D. M. Smith and R. T.
] Sutton, "A review of climate risk information for adaptation and

development planning," *International Journal of Climatology*, pp. 29(9), 1193-1215, 2009.

- [24 T. T. ARD, "A Review of Downscaling Methods for Climate Change
] Projections," United States Agency for International Development,
Burlington, 2014.
- [25 TIBCO, "What is a Neural Network?," 27 November 2022. [Online].
] Available: <https://www.tibco.com/reference-center/what-is-a-neural-network>.
- [26 K. Pang, "Self-organizing Maps," 1 September 2003. [Online]. Available:
] <https://www.cs.hmc.edu/~kpang/nn/som.html>.
- [27 C. Yin, "Applications of Self-Organizing Maps to Statistical Downscaling of
] Major Regional Climate Variables," 1 December 2011. [Online]. Available:
<https://researchcommons.waikato.ac.nz/handle/10289/5733>.
- [28 C. B. Chisanga, E. Phiri and V. R. N. Chinene, "Statistical Downscaling of
] Precipitation and Temperature Using Long Ashton Research Station
Weather Generator in Zambia: A Case of Mount Makulu Agriculture
Research Station," *American Journal of Climate Change*, pp. 6, 487-512,
2017.
- [29 P. G. Jones and P. K. Thornton, "Generating downscaled weather data from
] a suite of climate models for agricultural modelling applications,"
Agricultural Systems, pp. 1-5, 2013.
- [30 ILRI, "MarkSim DSSAT weather file generator," 1 1 2014. [Online].
] Available: <https://gisweb.ciat.cgiar.org/MarkSimGCM/>.
- [31 T. Zhang, W. S. Chandler, J. M. Hoell, D. Westberg, C. H. Whitlock and P.
] W. Stackhouse, "A Global Perspective on Renewable Energy Resources:
Nasa's Prediction of Worldwide Energy Resources (Power) Project,"
Proceedings of ISES World Congress 2007 (Vol. I – Vol. V), Vols. I-V, pp.
2636-2640, 2008.
- [32 The NASA POWER Team, "About the Prediction Of Worldwide Energy
] Resources (POWER) Project," 4 3 2022. [Online]. Available:
<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/52116d331ff64e468fe9351fc1c76423>
- [33 The NASA Power Team, "Data Sources," [Online]. Available:
] <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/docs/methodology/data/sources/>.
- [34 Global Wind Atlas, "Introduction," [Online]. Available:
] <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/about/introduction>.
- [35 Global Wind Atlas, "Key Features," [Online]. Available:
] <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/about/KeyFeatures>.

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